

SPACE-BASED APPLICATIONS FOR TRANSPORT MONITORING AND MANAGEMENT

Transforming Transportation:
Navigating Challenges, Embracing
Innovation for an Efficient, Safe,
and Sustainable Future

About the Project

SPATRA develops downstream applications for **road and rail transport** based on Copernicus and EGNSS services. The project focuses on two challenges:

- **Road traffic** congestion and limited parking availability for freight vehicles
- Extreme heat impact on **rail infrastructure** and risk of rail buckling

Road Transport Application

SPATRA uses **Sentinel-2 data**, **EGNSS**, and **drone** imagery to detect trucks, identify congestion, and estimate parking availability. Combining satellite images, drone photos, and in-situ location data improves **route planning** and **arrival-time predictions**.

Pilot site

Border-crossing **Horgoš (Serbia–Hungary)**, supported by logistics company **Nelt**.

Rail Transport Application

SPATRA combines **Copernicus land-surface temperature data**, **Sentinel-2 indices**, **local measurements**, and **drone thermal images** to map heat exposure along rail tracks. This enables prediction of **rail temperature** and **early warnings** for rail-buckling risk.

Pilot site

- The pilot is supported by **Serbian Railway Infrastructure**.

How SPATRA Works

SPATRA integrates multiple data sources into one system:

- Copernicus EO data
- Galileo/EGNSS for authenticated positioning
- Drone-based RGB and thermal imaging
- In-situ data from vehicles and sensors
- Processing pipelines on a cloud-based platform

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